

The Role of Education Unions in the Selection of Educational Administrators

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Abstract

This study examines the role of education unions in the selection of school administrators in Turkey. Research shows that education unions can provide valuable information about the qualifications and characteristics necessary for effective school management and help identify potential candidates. However, problems such as prejudice, political pressure and subjective evaluations frequently arise in the election process. To create a fair and objective selection process, it is recommended to standardize evaluation methods and criteria, to maintain impartiality and objectivity in decision-making processes, and to encourage continuous professional development for school administrators. Cooperation

between education unions, pressure groups and school administrators are also important for improving the quality of education and ensuring that all students have access to quality education. With the adoption of these suggestions, a fair and objective management system can be established that will benefit the entire education system.

Keywords: *Education, Education Management, Selecting School Administrator, Education Unions, The Role of Education Unions on Selecting School Administrators.*

Introduction

The success of training is heavily reliant on effective management and leadership. School administrators play a crucial role in ensuring the delivery of quality education and the efficient and effective operation of schools. Education unions, which represent teachers, support staff, and other education professionals, are key stakeholders in the selection of school administrators. They can provide valuable information about the qualifications and characteristics required for effective school management, identify potential candidates, and serve as a system of checks and balances for the selection process. However, there are also potential disadvantages, such as conflicts of interest and bias against certain candidates.

This study aims to examine the role of education unions in the selection of school administrators. Specifically, it will explore the benefits and potential drawbacks of working in collaboration with education unions, as well as best practices for ensuring a fair and effective selection process. By better understanding the role of education unions in the selection of school administrators, education leaders can make informed decisions that benefit students, schools, and society.

1. The Union Movement in Education Sector

1.1. The Concept of Union

The concept and importance of unions vary from country to country, depending on their role in the economic, social, and political life of each nation. In

ancient Greece, unions emerged as professional associations formed by individuals from the same social class to protect and improve their working conditions and income levels. While employers can also form unions, they are primarily adopted by workers. In Turkish, the term "union" refers to both workers' and employers' unions (Tuncay & Savaş, 2006).

In Turkey, labour unions are the primary focus of society, despite the existence of employers' unions (Işıklı, 2012). Unions are seen as organizations established to protect the professional, social, and economic rights of employees (Güneş-Karaman ve Erdoğan, 2016). They are made up of individuals who come together for a common purpose and work in cooperation and coordination to achieve their goals (Başbuğ, 2016). Although unions were initially established to protect workers' rights and improve working conditions, over time, they have become organizations that affect politics and social structures (Şahin, 2018).

Unions are organizations established to solve the problems faced by individuals in the workplace, to protect and develop their common interests and rights. They represent the collective union of workers who practice a profession to protect their own interests, improve working conditions, and strengthen their social status (Kutlu, 2015). Today, the concept of unions is associated with civil society and is considered an indispensable institution of democracy. Unions aim to protect and improve the working conditions of their members through collective bargaining with employers. Their success depends largely on their bargaining power, which is based on employers' ability to restrict the supply of labour and their willingness to give up higher wages in negotiations (Şahin ve Akboğa, 2019).

According to Serim (1995), unionization has two purposes: professional and social. Unions function primarily as a means of seeking rights and solving professional problems. They also aim to create a just economic, political, and social order. The prohibition of endowment rights means the perpetuation of social and economic injustices.

Unions can take different forms, such as professional associations, workplace unions, industrial associations, and national confederations or

federations, depending on the members they represent and the level of organization (Çelik, 2015). The Industrial Revolution in England in the late 18th century transformed the methods of production and, therefore, labour relations. Workers realized that they could be collectively stronger against employers, and as a result, unions emerged (Şahin, 2018). The main functions of unions are to secure workers' interests and conditions of employment and to help them control the industry. Unions also arm their members against the unfair and discriminatory treatment of employers, aiding in matters concerning the interests of workers (Alkış & İnceyol, 2019).

1.2. The Development of Unionism in Turkey

Unions have had varied organisational structures and functions across different countries and have encountered various pressures and restrictions throughout history. However, with the recognition of social rights by governments in the 19th century, unions gained more legitimacy and expanded their activities (Candoğan, 2015).

The historical development of unionism is a complex and dynamic process that spans centuries and continents. From its origins in the early days of the Industrial Revolution to its evolution in response to changing economic and political conditions, unionism has played a critical role in the struggle for workers' rights and social justice. The movement aimed at organizing and empowering workers through collective action has been both celebrated and denounced. It has faced numerous difficulties and failures throughout its historical process. Despite these challenges, unionism remains a vital force in many countries, continuing to shape the course of history as a driving force for change and progress (Şahinkaya, 2012; Eşiyok, 2009; Kayalidere, Şahin, 2014):

In this context, the journey of unionism in Turkey has also been quite challenging. The chronology of the development of unionism in Turkey is as follows:

- In the 1930s, a protectionist and statist understanding prevailed in Turkey, and the state's intervention in the economy increased. With the Labor Law enacted in 1936, unions were recognized institutionally, but strikes were prohibited. Although the Law on Societies enacted in 1938 made it free to establish all kinds of societies, the establishment of class societies was prohibited.
- In 1946, the relevant article of the Law on Societies of 1938, which prohibited the establishment of class associations, was abolished, and the Law on Workers' and Employers' Unions and Union Unions was enacted. The 1960 Constitution strengthened the working class's hand against capital with the unionization current and caused the destabilization of the regime of capital accumulation.
- The 1982 Constitution limited the collective rights introduced by the 1961 Constitution. After the administration was handed over to civilians in Turkey in 1983, attempts were made to maintain the Union Law, the Law on Collective Agreements, Strikes and Lockouts, and the Law on Meetings and Demonstrations by enacting them.
- As the labour market develops in Turkey, as well as all over the world, the concept of union has expanded to include all employees, including public officials. As a result of this expansion, unionization was started in the education sector.

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1.3. Education Unions in Turkey

With the introduction of multi-party politics, union rights, which are essential for democracy, have been recognized. Unions aim to improve working conditions and protect and develop the rights and interests of their members in terms of social rights (Güneş-Karaman ve Erdoğan, 2016). Unions are also pressure

groups with political influence. Reasons for joining unions include having similar or common views on profiteering methods, class consciousness, balancing inequality between employer and employee, unity against management, benefiting from union effectiveness or benefits, social pressure, and coercion (Akcan, Polat ve Ölçüm, 2017).

The liberal policies brought about by globalization transformed Turkey after the 1980s. As a result of the long struggle of civil servants, union rights were legally recognized in 2001. In 2012, the legal framework of union rights for public servants took its final form (Cengiz, 2019). Education unions have been at the forefront of the struggle for public unionization due to their numerical superiority within the public sector. After the adoption of the 1982 Constitution in Turkey, education unions began to be established, and the first union established for teachers was the Education Sector Public Servants Union. After this union, the Education, Science and Culture Workers Union, the Union of Educators Union, and the Turkish Education Union were established. Today, a total of 49 unions are active in the education sector, the largest of which are Eğitim Bir-Sen (34.2%), Türk Eğitim Sen (20.03%), Eğitim-Sen (6.23%), and Eğitim İş Sendikaları (6.147%) (Ministry of Labour and Social Security, 2022).

Previous research on education unions in Turkey has mostly focused on their expectations and problems. For example, Güneş-Karaman and Erdoğan (2016) conducted a qualitative study to determine the primary objectives of education unions in Turkey, the expectations of their members, and their main problems. The research design used was phenomenology, and the data were collected through semi-structured interviews. The participants were selected from Istanbul managers and members of the four largest education unions (Eğitim-Bir-Sen, Türk Eğitim-Sen, Eğitim-Sen, and Eğitim-İş). The collected data were analysed using the content analysis technique. The results of the study revealed that the primary objectives of education unions in the education sector are to ensure basic rights, improve the quality of education, and protect the rights of employees. Likewise, the expectations of union members are to defend their rights and contribute to the improvement of

the quality of education. According to managers and members, the main problems of education unions are that they are perceived as depending on political parties or ideologies, negative perceptions and prejudices against unions, and the lack of the right to strike.

Kayıkçı (2013) conducted quantitative research to examine the current situation of education unions and determine the expectations of teachers and school administrators working in primary and secondary schools from their unions. In the 2009-2010 academic year, a sample of 661 teachers and administrators working in 27 primary and 20 secondary schools in Antalya province was surveyed. The research results showed that unionization rates have increased in both the public and private sectors and that proximity to power has positively affected the number of members in unions. Therefore, teachers who have ambitions to rise think that they can move forward with education managers by preferring unions that are close to power.

2. Educational Administration and Selection of Educational Administrators

2.1. Educational Administration

The field of educational administration began to be studied scientifically in the 19th century, but programs specifically designed to train educational administrators appeared much later. Traditional and modern management approaches have influenced educational management, which is related to the effective operation, management, and development of institutions established to meet the educational needs of society (Bayrak, 2019). The traditional approach to educational management prioritizes bureaucracy and hierarchy, taking little account of individual needs and expectations. However, the postmodern paradigm has led to changes in the roles of teachers and administrators, with a shift from the concept of education manager to that of education leader. Education leaders are expected to develop long-term strategic plans, consider the values and motivations of all stakeholders, and can resolve conflicts and use political force (Aydoğan, 2015).

Therefore, as the postmodern paradigm is accepted, the issue of choosing education administrators has become more important.

Educational management is a critical area that needs attention, especially when the factors that increase its importance, such as the realities of the country and the problems in the education system, are taken into consideration. For this reason, training managers need to undergo training that will enable them to acquire the necessary management skills, including academic training that provides the scientific approach. However, the fact that education managers are often assigned to their duties in Turkey without having the necessary knowledge, experience, and skills leads to ineffective decision-making and problem-solving methods (Aytuntaş, Demirdağ and Ertem, 2020). This is since education management is not seen as a special profession, and managerial duties are often seen as additional duties.

2.2. Selection of Education Managers in the World

Effective educational management includes creating a democratic and inclusive learning environment, managing resources, overseeing the curriculum and educational process, supporting the academic and social progress of all individuals, and fostering a positive school culture. School leaders must have the ability to develop a clear mission and vision for the school, facilitate collaboration between teachers and administrators, and apply effective management techniques that are compatible with evolving organizational and educational theories (Arabacı, Şanlı & Altun, 2015).

Selecting and training effective school leaders is important to achieve educational goals and raise a successful generation. There is an ongoing debate as to whether educational management is a formal, scientific field that can be taught in universities or a skill that needs to be learned through practice and leadership qualities (Savaş, 2019). It is important to examine the different practices for selecting school leaders worldwide to identify strengths and weaknesses and improve selection and educational processes. In addition, school leaders must be

trained to adapt to the changing organizational management environment and apply techniques that are compatible with evolving theories (Gülmez & Yavuz, 2016).

The selection and training of educational administrators vary from country to country. In the United States, school principals are expected to be highly competent and participate in in-service training during and prior to their tenure. The requirements to become a school administrator in the United States are usually to have a master's degree in educational administration, have a teaching background, and obtain certification from an educational leadership program. In addition, school boards and teachers' associations have significant influence over school administration and education policy (Öztürk & Akkuş, 2020).

Each state in Germany has its own education policy and education system, and the laws on the selection and appointment of education administrators vary from state to state. In France, it is necessary to be a teacher to be an education administrator, and the selection and appointment are made by the Ministry of Education. Italy has seen changes in the education system with efforts to make school management more autonomous. In Japan, school principals are considered teachers and must have at least 20 years of teaching experience before they can be considered for the position of principal. The country places a strong emphasis on seniority (Öz, 2019).

2.3. Selection of Educational Administrators in Turkey

Rapid global transformations and innovations have impacted the expected behaviour and competencies of managers, including training managers. Thus, it is crucial for training managers to understand their roles and effectively implement these changes. In Turkey, where experienced and well-trained personnel and resources are often in short supply, it is vital to train training managers to meet the required standards of competence and expertise. This will optimise the use of available materials and human resources and ensure educational management is considered a specialised profession (Güçlü, Şahin, Yavuz-Tabak & Sönmez, 2016).

Despite the various policies regarding the selection and appointment of education administrators in Turkey, stability has not been achieved. School administrators can take office without acquiring the standard knowledge and qualifications required for educational management, making it essential to train them to ensure they can effectively manage the available resources (Uygur, 2021). The training of education managers in Turkey can be divided into three periods: the apprenticeship model, educational sciences model, and in-service training model, but the first two models have not been successful in equipping educational leaders. Thereupon, the Central Government Organization Research Project (MEHTAP) report in 1962 suggested opening programs to train education administrators in universities (Karabatak, 2015). In 1998, the Ministry of National Education established an examination system to select qualified teachers, and in 1999, the Ministry stated the need to train pre-service education administrators. Although the 120-hour program aimed at increasing the competence of education administrators was very beneficial for the participants, the abolition of the pre-service education and education administrator selection exam in 2004 and 2007 was seen as a retrospective practice in the field of education administration. The regulation on the appointment of education managers in 2015 and 2016 determined the evaluation criteria for oral and written exams (Konan, Çetin & Yılmaz, 2017). However, the policies on the selection and appointment of educational administrators in Turkey have not provided a stable and systematic selection and appointment system.

Despite progress in graduate education management programs in Turkey, the Ministry of National Education has not yet utilised these programs to train school administrators. Moreover, there is no cooperation between the Ministry and universities in the training of education administrators. As of 2023, the election and appointment of education administrators are made in accordance with the Regulation on the Selection and Appointment of Administrators to the Educational Institutions Affiliated to the Ministry of National Education. This regulation obliges candidates to take the written and oral exam and sets out general and special conditions to be met for persons to be appointed as managers.

The selection of education administrators in Turkey is influenced by various pressure groups and associations, including education unions.

3. The Role of Unions in the Selection of Education Managers

Education unions are organizations that represent workers in the education sector and contribute to the social and professional development of their members, as well as their living conditions. They also have an impact on education policy and play a crucial role in implementing practices that can improve education, especially on issues that the government may not be aware of. Education unions are effective pressure groups, working in coordination and cooperation to create a competent community of civil servants and solve problems in educational administration. Their activities include coordinating, guiding, and executing pedagogical and administrative actions to increase efficiency and effectiveness in schools.

However, the activities of unions in schools are always influenced by power dynamics, and education unions are seen as structures with political influence. Nevertheless, the existence of educational associations in schools is essential for the development of educational administration and cooperation with factors affecting education. It is a situation that can and should have a positive impact on the quality of education.

No standardized assessment method has been introduced for the qualifications of education managers, and many pressure groups, including education unions, have an informal influence on the selection process of education managers in Turkey. This has led to a departure from the principle of merit, which raises concerns about impartiality and fairness in the electoral process. The appointment of educational administrators is also influenced by political orientations, and many appointments are not made objectively. Among the factors influencing the selection of school principals in Turkey are unions, pressure groups, bilateral relations, and the principle of merit (Erol, 2020).

Previous research on the role of unions in the selection of education managers has also yielded findings in this direction. For example, Dermenci and

Balyer (2021) investigated the views of school administrators on the role of teachers' unions in the selection of education administrators in Turkey. They interviewed 16 school administrators who are members of the four largest teachers' associations in the country, using a semi-structured interview form, and analysed the data using content analysis. The study found that school administrators believe that teachers' unions influence the selection process of education administrators, with some perceiving their impact as positive, and others as negative. Additionally, most education administrators believe that teachers' unions do not significantly influence the development of education policies for the selection of school administrators, but they should play a more active role in this process.

In another study, Özüdoğru (2019) conducted qualitative research with 20 school administrators in the Odunpazarı district of Eskişehir province during the 2017-2018 academic year. Using the phenomenology pattern, the study aimed to determine the opinions of school administrators on the application of the principle of merit in their elections, identify the problems encountered in the application of the principle of merit, and develop suggestions for these problems. The findings revealed that school administrators view merit as the ability to perform a task well and deserving to be in a position, but they believe that the application of the principle of merit in the selection of school administrators is hindered by union discrimination, political pressure, and subjective evaluations. In response to this problem, the administrators proposed giving priority to graduate education, establishing a merit committee for written exams and practical interviews, and structuring the process to be free from external pressure and discrimination.

Similarly, Konan, Çetin, and Yılmaz (2017) conducted a qualitative survey to determine the criteria, process, and possible outcomes perceived by teachers for the appointment of school principals in Turkey. The results showed that a fairer, objective, and merit-based evaluation process is required in the appointment of directors. According to Akcan, Polat, and Measurement (2017), the reasons why educators are members of unions are predominantly political pressure and political views, as well as reasons for not being a member of unions. Therefore, unions are

seen as a political structure rather than an organization aimed at seeking rights, at least in the education sector. This increases the unions' efforts to bring their members to the forefront as a pressure factor in the selection of education administrators.

Conclusion

The role of teachers' unions in the selection of school administrators is an important topic of discussion in the Turkish education system. Research has revealed that some school administrators believe that teachers' unions influence the selection process, while others think that education unions should play a more active role in the development of education policies for selecting school administrators.

However, the application of the principle of merit in the selection process faces problems such as union discrimination, political pressure, and subjective evaluations. To solve these issues, proposals such as the establishment of a merit committee for graduate education, written exams, and practical interviews have been presented by school administrators.

While education unions play an important role as representatives of education workers, their effectiveness can be influenced by factors such as exposure to political influences and conflicts of interest. Therefore, cooperation between education unions, education managers, and pressure groups should be ensured, and a fair and objective management system should be established to improve the quality of education.

Creating a fair, objective, and merit-based management system in the selection of school administrators will help improve the education system. Additionally, education unions can play an important role in improving the education system by defending the rights of education workers. Therefore, a manager appointment process based on merit and without subjective evaluation criteria should be applied. In this context, the implementation of the following recommendations will increase the quality of the education system:

- Standardization of assessment methods for training managers should be ensured, and objective and transparent selection criteria and processes should be established to select education managers based on merit, not political affiliations, or prejudices.
- Education unions should continue to play an active role in the development of education policies, but they should also maintain their impartiality and objectivity in decision-making processes.
- Education unions and pressure groups should work more closely with education managers to identify and address factors that may hinder the quality of education, ensuring that all students have access to high-quality education.
- Education managers should be encouraged to pursue further education and training to improve their qualifications and professional development, equipping them with the necessary knowledge and skills to manage schools effectively.

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